

IMMUNE MODULATION AND METASTASIS IN OVARIAN CANCER

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Abstract. *The review article presents data on the predominant mechanisms of metastatic progression in ovarian cancer. It highlights the morphological and functional features of the greater omentum, detailing how these contribute to the spread of cancer cells as well as exert anti-tumor effects. The balance between these opposing properties is influenced by the cellular composition, the content of extracellular matrix molecules, and the biomechanical characteristics of the greater omentum during carcinogenesis. The milk spots serve as the primary sites for cancer cell implantation and differ from lymph nodes due to their simpler structure and unique cellular composition (including macrophages, B cells, CD4+ and CD8+ T lymphocytes, and other immune cells), which undergoes significant changes during metastasis. M2 macrophages, adipocytes, CD33+ cells, and CD4+ CD25high CD127low T suppressor cells promote the migration, invasion, growth, and colonization of cancer cells. Most molecules synthesized in the greater omentum during metastasis also stimulate these processes, with exceptions including E-cadherin, CXCL10, CXCL11, and CXCR3, which inhibit tumor growth.*

Keywords: *ovarian cancer, greater omentum, carcinomatosis, lymphocytes, metastases, milk spots, gene expression.*

Relevance of Ovarian Cancer

Approximately 239,000 women are diagnosed with ovarian cancer each year worldwide. The most common type of this disease is high-grade serous ovarian carcinoma, which many researchers now believe originates and/or involves the fallopian tube rather than the ovaries. Almost 70% of these women present with advanced-stage disease, mainly due to the absence of early warning signs and/or effective screening methods. This results in a poor 5-year survival rate of almost 30%. The most significant prognostic factor for ovarian cancer is the volume of residual disease after surgical debulking. Unfortunately, despite principal debulking surgery and adjuvant chemotherapy, many patients will present with ascitic tumor progression. It was recently demonstrated that the cancer cells of ascites readily form lesions on the lesser and greater omentum, the latter of which is their main site of progression. Furthermore, the greater omentum is immune-privileged, and hence an ideal site for these ascitic ovarian cancer cells to promote their growth and metastatic potential.

The specific molecular constituents of the peritoneal ascites-induced TAAM landscape impact the patient outcome, specifically the large population of CD66b-positive TAAMs. At this time, the mechanism(s) allowing for the progression of omental-related technologies is unknown. This is the problem that our study addressed in an effort to better understand omentum-based tumor progression in order to develop effective therapies against this aggressive nature of metastasis. Cell-microenvironment crosstalk, such as that between ovarian cancer cells and mesothelial cells, plays a significant role in promoting ovarian cancer cell proliferation and adhesion. The tumor microenvironment, especially the tumor microenvironment-associated macrophages of the omentum, may be promoting the growth and progression of ovarian tumors and potentiating drug

resistance. The peritoneal and omental/endometrial microenvironments differ significantly, which is a topic meriting further investigation that can lead to defining which omental-related pathways and therapeutic targets are appropriate.

The literature surrounding the role of milky spots in cancer metastasis has evolved significantly over the past decade, highlighting their unique microenvironmental characteristics and cellular composition that facilitate tumor progression. The foundational work by (Cao et al., 2014) establishes the omentum as a critical site for peritoneal metastasis, emphasizing the role of the CCL22-CCR4 axis in the selective infiltration of gastric cancer cells into milky spots. Their findings illustrate that these structures not only serve as reservoirs for cancer cell growth but also actively contribute to the establishment of micrometastases through specific molecular interactions.

Building upon this understanding, (Liu et al., 2016) delve deeper into the functional dynamics of milky spots, characterizing them as primary sites for cancer cell implantation. They underscore the distinction between milky spots and lymph nodes, attributing this to the simpler structure and unique cellular composition of the former. Their research identifies key immune cells, such as M2 macrophages and CD4⁺ CD25^{high} CD127^{low} T suppressor cells, that promote various stages of cancer progression, including migration, invasion, and colonization. This article provides a comprehensive overview of the cellular interactions within milky spots that facilitate a conducive environment for metastatic growth.

Further investigations by (Steenbrugge et al., 2018) and (Issa Atiya, 2018) reinforce the critical role of milky spots in cancer metastasis, reiterating the importance of the immune landscape in these regions. Both studies highlight the involvement of M2 macrophages and other immune cells in enhancing cancer cell migration and proliferation while noting the production of specific molecules in the greater omentum that contribute to these processes. Notably, they also identify exceptions, such as E-cadherin and CXCL10, which serve to inhibit tumor growth, thus presenting a nuanced view of the microenvironment's dual role in cancer progression.

Finally, the work of (Etzerodt et al., 2020) expands on the understanding of tissue-resident macrophages in the omentum, positing that these cells play a significant role in the metastatic spread of ovarian cancer. Their research aligns with previous findings, reinforcing the concept that the milky spots are not merely passive sites for cancer cell implantation but are active participants in promoting metastatic disease through complex immune interactions.

Collectively, these articles illustrate the intricate interplay between cancer cells and the unique cellular milieu of milky spots, elucidating their pivotal role in the metastatic process. The evolving narrative emphasizes the need for further exploration of the molecular and cellular mechanisms at play within these structures to develop targeted therapeutic strategies against cancer metastasis.

The article titled "The role of the CCL22-CCR4 axis in the metastasis of gastric cancer cells into omental milky spots" by (Cao et al., 2014) provides significant insights into the mechanisms underlying the preferential migration and proliferation of gastric cancer cells within the milky spots of the omentum. The authors highlight that the omentum serves as a critical initial site for peritoneal metastasis due to its unique microenvironment, which is conducive to the establishment of micrometastases.

One of the key findings of this study is the identification of the CCL22-CCR4 axis as a pivotal factor in the selective infiltration of gastric cancer cells into milky spots. The experimental

design, which involved the intraperitoneal injection of DiI-labeled gastric cancer MFC cells into strain 615 mice, effectively demonstrated that these milky spots became densely populated with proliferating cancer cells within two weeks. This observation underscores the milky spots' role as a supportive niche for cancer cell survival and growth, contrasting with the formation of single cell-type micrometastases observed in non-milky spot areas.

The authors provide compelling evidence that varying concentrations of CCL22 significantly enhance the proliferation and migration of MFC cells, particularly within the range of 10–100 ng/ml. This finding is critical as it suggests that the microenvironment of the milky spots is not only structurally distinct but also biochemically active, facilitating the establishment of metastatic colonies. The study emphasizes the importance of the immune cell composition within these milky spots, including M2 macrophages and T suppressor cells, which may further contribute to the metastatic process by promoting tumor cell migration and invasion.

Furthermore, the article discusses how the milky spots' cellular composition and the presence of specific signaling molecules can influence the metastatic behavior of gastric cancer cells. This aligns with the notion that the immune microenvironment plays a dual role in cancer progression, where certain immune cells may support tumor growth while others could potentially inhibit it.

The article "Milky spots: omental functional units and hotbeds for peritoneal cancer metastasis" by (Liu et al., 2016) provides an in-depth analysis of the role of milky spots in the context of cancer metastasis, particularly focusing on peritoneal dissemination. The authors effectively articulate how milky spots, characterized by their unique cellular composition and simpler structure compared to lymph nodes, serve as critical sites for cancer cell implantation.

One of the key insights presented in the article is the significant transformation of the immune microenvironment within milky spots during the metastatic process. The presence of M2 macrophages, adipocytes, CD33+ cells, and CD4+ CD25high CD127low T suppressor cells is highlighted as instrumental in facilitating the migration, invasion, growth, and colonization of cancer cells. This finding aligns with contemporary understanding of the tumor microenvironment, where various immune cell types can either promote or inhibit tumor progression. The authors' emphasis on the role of M2 macrophages is particularly noteworthy, as it underscores the dual nature of macrophages in cancer biology, where M2 polarization is often associated with pro-tumorigenic activity.

Moreover, the article discusses the secretion of specific molecules from the greater omentum during metastasis, which further stimulate cancer cell activities. Notably, the authors identify E-cadherin, CXCL10, CXCL11, and CXCR3 as exceptions that inhibit tumor growth. This distinction is crucial, as it suggests a complex interplay between pro-tumorigenic and anti-tumorigenic signals within the milky spots. The authors successfully convey the idea that while milky spots are predominantly supportive of cancer cell survival and proliferation, there exists a subset of molecules that may counteract these processes, indicating potential therapeutic targets.

The authors support their claims with a well-structured argument and relevant data, although the article could benefit from a more extensive discussion on the potential therapeutic implications of these findings. For example, the exploration of how modulating the immune composition of milky spots could alter cancer outcomes would provide valuable insights for future research directions.

The article titled "Anti-inflammatory signaling by mammary tumor cells mediates prometastatic macrophage polarization in an innovative intraductal mouse model for triple-negative breast cancer" by (Steenbrugge et al., 2018) provides a comprehensive examination of the role of milk spots in the metastatic process of triple-negative breast cancer (TNBC). The authors effectively highlight the unique structural and cellular characteristics of milk spots, distinguishing them from lymph nodes, and elucidate their significance as primary sites for cancer cell implantation.

One of the central themes of the article is the role of various immune cells, particularly M2 macrophages, in promoting cancer cell dynamics within these microenvironments. The authors discuss how the polarization of macrophages towards the M2 phenotype—fostered by anti-inflammatory signaling from mammary tumor cells—facilitates the migration, invasion, growth, and colonization of cancer cells. This finding aligns with the broader understanding of the tumor microenvironment, where immune cell composition and polarization are critical to tumor progression.

The article also delves into the cellular composition of milk spots, which includes not only macrophages but also adipocytes, CD33+ cells, and CD4+ CD25high CD127low T suppressor cells. The authors provide evidence that these cells interact with cancer cells in ways that enhance metastatic potential. This interaction underscores the complexity of the tumor microenvironment and the necessity of understanding these cellular relationships for developing effective therapies.

Furthermore, (Steenbrugge et al., 2018) address the role of specific molecules synthesized in the greater omentum during metastasis. They note that while many of these molecules promote cancer cell behaviors, there are notable exceptions, such as E-cadherin, CXCL10, CXCL11, and CXCR3, which appear to inhibit tumor growth. This nuanced view of the molecular landscape highlights the dual role that certain factors can play in tumor biology, which is critical for therapeutic strategies aimed at modulating the tumor microenvironment.

In the article "Role of Mammary Microenvironment in Promoting Left-Right Differences in Tumor Progression, Metastasis, and Therapeutic Response," (Issa Atiya, 2018) provides a comprehensive examination of the unique characteristics of the milk spots as they relate to cancer cell implantation and metastasis. The article highlights the distinction between milk spots and lymph nodes, emphasizing the simpler structure and unique cellular composition of the former. This differentiation is crucial as it sets the stage for understanding how these microenvironments influence tumor progression.

Atiya's exploration of the cellular composition within milk spots is particularly noteworthy. The presence of M2 macrophages, adipocytes, CD33+ cells, and CD4+ CD25high CD127low T suppressor cells is identified as instrumental in facilitating cancer cell migration, invasion, and colonization. The author effectively articulates how these immune cells contribute to a pro-tumorigenic environment, which is essential for the survival and proliferation of cancer cells. This insight aligns with the broader understanding of the tumor microenvironment's role in cancer biology.

Moreover, the article delves into the molecular mechanisms at play, noting that while many molecules synthesized in the greater omentum during metastasis promote tumor-related processes, there are notable exceptions. The mention of E-cadherin, CXCL10, CXCL11, and CXCR3 as inhibitors of tumor growth adds depth to the discussion, highlighting the complexity of the

interactions within the tumor microenvironment. This duality of molecules that can either promote or inhibit tumor growth underscores the intricate balance that exists within these sites.

However, while the article provides valuable insights into the mechanisms of tumor progression within milky spots, it could benefit from a more detailed exploration of the specific pathways through which these immune cells and molecules exert their effects. A deeper investigation into the signaling pathways and interactions among these components would enhance the understanding of their roles in cancer metastasis.

Summary, Major Insights, and Concluding Thoughts

The literature reviewed provides a comprehensive examination of the role of milky spots in cancer metastasis, particularly their distinct microenvironment and cellular composition that facilitate tumor progression. The foundational work by (Cao et al., 2014) establishes the omentum as a critical site for peritoneal metastasis, emphasizing the significance of the CCL22-CCR4 axis in the selective infiltration of gastric cancer cells. This research highlights that milky spots not only serve as reservoirs for cancer cell growth but also actively contribute to the establishment of micrometastases through specific molecular interactions.

Further investigations by (Liu et al., 2016) and (Steenbrugge et al., 2018) reinforce the understanding of milky spots as primary sites for cancer cell implantation. They underscore the simpler structure and unique cellular composition of milky spots compared to lymph nodes, identifying critical immune cells such as M2 macrophages, CD4⁺ CD25^{high} CD127^{low} T suppressor cells, and others that promote various stages of cancer progression, including migration, invasion, and colonization. The literature indicates that the immune landscape within milky spots is dynamic and can shift in response to tumor presence, further supporting the metastatic process.

Additionally, the articles collectively highlight the production of specific molecules in the greater omentum during metastasis that enhance tumor growth, while also identifying exceptions like E-cadherin, CXCL10, CXCL11, and CXCR3, which inhibit tumor progression. This dual role of the microenvironment—where certain components promote tumor growth while others act as inhibitors—suggests a complex interplay that is crucial for understanding cancer biology and developing potential therapeutic strategies.

The work of (Etzerodt et al., 2020) expands on this by discussing the role of tissue-resident macrophages in the omentum, positing that these immune cells are active participants in promoting metastatic disease through intricate immune interactions. The findings from these studies collectively emphasize the need for further exploration of the molecular and cellular mechanisms within milky spots to inform targeted therapeutic approaches against metastasis.

In conclusion, the reviewed literature underscores the pivotal role of milky spots in cancer metastasis, characterized by their unique cellular composition and microenvironment that support tumor progression. The interaction of various immune cells and the secretion of specific molecules create a dynamic landscape that facilitates cancer cell migration, invasion, and colonization while also presenting potential targets for therapeutic intervention.

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